

A MANAGERIAL PERSPECTIVE OVER THE CHANGES IN THE EDUCATION OF THE POST PANDEMIC SOCIETY

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Abstract

Purpose – Because the COVID-19 Pandemic has accelerated digitization of the Romanian education system, Romania could be in 2022 the country where the transition to digitalization of the education could have the most accentuated rhythm among all European countries, although Romania ranks 27th of 27 European Union Member States in the 2021 edition of the Digital Economy and Society Index. The accelerated use of Information and Communication Technology during COVID-19 Pandemic, will change the future of the Romanian Higher Education System?

Methodology/approach - The research methodology was based on two surveys performed through questionnaires. First was composed of 18 questions and applied to a population of 700 respondents and the survey period was between 2 and 7 May 2022. The investigated population, the respondents, were students of the University of Petroșani at the bachelor and master studies. The second questionnaire had 19 questions and was applied on 59 teachers of the University of Petroșani and the survey period was 3 and 5 March 2022.

Findings – Society in general and the higher education system in particular have changed after 2 years of pandemic. All those involved, students and teachers, believe that the process of change is still ongoing.

Research limitations/implications – Even if the respondents, as mentioned, are only from the University of Petroșani, the study can be extrapolated to provide an image for the Romanian education system.

Practical implications – Even if one of the most severely affected areas of human activity by the COVID-19 pandemic was education, now in the post pandemic reality one of the benefits of this pandemic will be probably the re modelling of the educational system, most likely the higher one, in a hybrid format.

Originality/value – The purpose of this research is to find the best method for adapting the University of Petroșani as quickly as possible to the new context of hybrid education model that is being implemented in Romanian higher education system.

Key words: Romanian education system, COVID-19, Mixed education, Digital education, Management perspective

Introduction and background literature

The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic in education have been a concern for all those involved in this field, pupils, students and their parents, teachers, researchers, leaders in education, government. This concern meant the effort to adapt to the new conditions, but also the preparation for the post-pandemic period. Because this preparation cannot be done without evaluating the effects, the researchers tried to identify which were the most relevant aspects highlighted by the pandemic time.

Thus, Ożadowicz, A. (2020) starts in his research from the premise that the blockage caused by the COVID-19 pandemic did not only have negative effects, as in fact happens every time when an impact event occurs. Forcing the decision makers to find solutions to support the education system during the period of blockage, eventually led to a discussion on the need to modernize teaching methods. According to Ożadowicz, A. (2020) the possibility of using combined and hybrid learning is feasible and

to be researched, so that students to benefit from an improved learning framework. (Ożadowicz, A., 2020) Lau, S.S.S. et al. (2021) conducted a study to clarify whether the use of blended learning, experienced by Hong Kong during the COVID-19 pandemic, affects the model of creating a career course. The authors' conclusion led to the confirmation of the hypotheses that the use of this way of learning is beneficial. Therefore, the direction proposed by the authors aims to create a holistic curriculum on the full development of young people, with a view to a better transition for them in the labor market. (Lau, S.S.S. et al., 2021) The research conducted by Sobaih, A.E.E. et al. (2021) tried to determine the extent to which the use of social media or a dedicated tool such as Microsoft TEAMS were effective in supporting education in the Egyptian university environment, more specifically among hospitality students. While social media had the advantage of a better framework to receive the support of teachers or colleagues, Microsoft TEAMS was considered more suitable by students for the assessment component, but also for that related to real feedback. Thus, it is concluded that both the decision makers in education, but also the researchers who generate trends or changes in education should use these experiences appropriately. (Sobaih, A.E.E. et al., 2021). Most probably, if the universities that used Microsoft TEAMS during the pandemic period, had used other applications from the Microsoft family, such as Yammer, the research done by Sobaih, A.E.E. et al. (2021) would have had a slightly changed result. Alyahya, M.A. et al. (2022) analyzed the impact of imposing the use of e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic on students, from the perspective of gender differences, with the possibility of conducting this study in gender segregated cultures, as is the case in Saudi Arabia. The results of the study showed a better adaptation to e-learning for female students, who obtained better results. The study also indicated the need to combine conventional education with e-learning in the post-pandemic period. (Alyahya, M.A. et al., 2022) Kanetaki, Z. et al. (2022) performed an analysis of the results obtained by students, starting from the moment when the COVID19 pandemic was triggered, during which time the activity took place exclusively online and later, when they switched to a hybrid regime. The authors found that the need to study the theoretical component was explicitly relevant, the results obtained by students being affected by this component. The evaluation of the students had a good success rate, without being able to establish a relationship with the participation in the courses, either online or face to face. The analysis performed by Kanetaki, Z. et al. (2022) also allowed the development of a model for predicting the results obtained by students, which can provide the necessary support for better adaptation of the hybrid educational system to the needs of post-COVID society. (Kanetaki, Z., et al., 2022) Xing, X. et al. (2022) found that the quality of online education was affected by internet access and the environment in which students were during online classes. In addition, the authors found that one solution to overcome the disadvantage caused by Internet access for participation in synchronous online education is to use the blended learning system, which can increase the effectiveness of learning outcomes. (Xing, X. et al., 2022) Sobaih, A.E.E. et al. (2022) identified the need to study the use of social media application in education, in the absence of an e-learning management system. This situation was more common in developing countries and was practically the solution that was used during the pandemic of COVID-19, to support educational activity. Starting from today's youth culture and using the theory of planned behavior, along with the model of acceptance of technology, it was found that the analysis led to a useful conclusion, namely that social networks can be a major tool for communication in academia. Moreover, the integration of social networking resources for the higher education system, in the absence of a digital education management system, can become a good choice for strengthening the sustainability of universities. (Sobaih, A.E.E. et al., 2022) Escobio-Prieto, I. et al. (2021) identify through their study the downside of the forced transition to online education caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The analysis was done among health science students and found that physical therapy students suffered greatly during the emergency caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. In addition, it was found that universities had tools to enable virtual education, but that these tools were rarely used before the state of emergency. What is relevant to this study is that it highlights the need for continuous observation of student satisfaction, closely related to the possibility of using a very well-balanced hybrid education system. (Escobio-Prieto, I. et al. 2021)

Methodology

The research methodology was based on a survey performed through a questionnaire containing 19 questions and applied on 59 teachers of the University of Petrosani, during 3-5 March 2022. This managerial research was based on the answers provided by 59 teachers of the University of Petroşani, that represent 59% of the investigated teachers and 45% of the total of the university teachers, so it was a representative research (Figure 1). The 19 questions of the survey were organized into 3 sections and 10 directions that could support the future development of the University of Petrosani in the authors

opinion, and the relevance of the respondents from the perspective of teaching degree of the teaching staff is 45%.

Figure 1. The relevance of the respondents from the perspective of teaching degree of the teaching staff.

Findings and discussions

We are at the moment when the prospect of returning to the context before the onset of the global pandemic caused by COVID19 no longer exists and not because we no longer want to, but because the world has changed. We have all changed, but society has changed the most, the younger generations have undergone essential changes. We can look to the past for an analysis, but much more important is to look to the future using the experience of everyone in this period.

As is already known, in Romania, article 139 of the National Education Law was changed in May 2022 "...Some activities in the form of face-to-face education can be carried out through the specific electronic, information and technology communications resources, settled in quality standards developed and approved by ARACIS" (Romanian Agency for Quality Assurance in Higher Education). (Romanian Parliament, 2022) The authors have anticipated these changes of the Romanian HEI and in their papers published last year stated that, "...education will become, in future, more and more a hybrid one". (Edelhauser E., et al., 2021)

In this context the answers to the first question of the survey applied to the teachers of the University of Petrosani, showed in Figure 2 that teachers anticipated the changes of the HEI system, two months before and consider in a 70 to 80 percent, that probably we will have fundamental changes in the education system in the post pandemic society.

Being a small university of Romania focused more on education than on research and development, University of Petrosani has a few deficiencies in the field of research. Also, because inside the Romanian HEI the competition and rankings are based more on research results (Ministry of Education, 2022b), the teachers indicated the first priorities as creating research teams with scientific production and involvement of teachers in research projects. But after the two pandemic years, the third priority mentioned was the development of educational platforms, considering that the future education will be a hybrid one, as it can be seen in Figure 3 as a result of question 3.

Because education in Romania is underfunded (The Fiscal Council of Romania, 2021) and because the salaries of young teachers are low, a possibility to supplement salaries is represented by the involvement of university staff in the implementation of projects. In this context the answers to question 6 showed that the development of a department dedicated to writing funding applications for projects, represent the first priority in the teacher opinion, and developing a hub for creativity, innovation and invention or a research development cluster, represent only the second option (Figure 4).

Analyzing the academic campus development as a pillar of a future development of the university, the authors have investigated the teachers of the University of Petrosani, regarding the priorities of the academic campus development, and because our university is a comprehensive one, but mainly focused on engineering, the most important direction must be the upgrading of the laboratory equipment (Figure 5).

Figure 2. Question1 - Do you consider that the Romania Higher Education Institutions (HEI) will suffer a fundamental transformation into the post-COVID era? Evaluate the change by the importance of the following aspects

Figure 3. Question 3 Which should be the development priorities of the University of Petroșani for the next years?

Another problem of the Romanian education system is the financing of the universities based on the number of students, and in this context the first option of the teachers for increasing the economic efficiency is to rise the number of the students, even if stimulating research excellence to increase the funding obtained by the university from the government and a more efficient use of the human resources represent much more normal options for increasing the economic efficiency of a HEI (Figure 6).

Figure 4. Question 6 Research Pillar - the complement of education. Which should be the priorities of the University of Petroșani in supporting the research activity?

Figure 5. Question 8 Academic Campus Pillar. Which should be the priorities related to the development of the University of Petroșani academic campus?

In the context of the answers offered to question 10 (Figure 7), the authors hope that adapting the classrooms with videoconference equipment and training of teachers for online education will be a priority of the University of Petrosani in the following 10 years, according to the project that will be implemented through - Grants for the digitization of universities funded by PNRR 2022 (Ministry of European Investments and Projects, 2021) - Component C15: Education Reform 5 (Ministry of Education, 2022a): Adopt the legislative framework for the digitization of education - Investment 16: Digitization of universities and their preparation for the digital professions of the future.

Conclusions

The research carried out by the authors using as respondents 59% of the university teachers, teachers that will constitute the academic body that will support the implementation of the management plan of the future rector of the University of Petrosani for the term 2024-2028, is unique for the University of Petrosani. The survey had the role of structuring a future management plan but also identifying the development priorities of the university in a new hybrid education context, two months before the ministry of education have decided that the 2022/2023 academic year should be a hybrid one.

Figure 6. Question 9 Economic Efficiency Pillar. Which should be the University of Petroșani strategy to increase efficiency?

Figure 7. Question 10 - Educational Infrastructure Pillar - What do you consider priorities for a future education in the hybrid model at UPET?

After two years of online education, the concept of academic education in Romania is completely different, a fact revealed also by a second research conducted by the authors. This survey was composed of 18 questions and applied to a population of 700 respondents and the survey period was between 2 and 7 May 2022. The investigated population, the respondents, were students of the University of Petroșani at the bachelor and master studies. The results of this research will be presented by the authors in other papers.

The authors conclude that any academic vision for the future development of HEI must take into account this new context of hybrid education, and also the options of teachers and students of that university.

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